

TESTING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST: A FIELD STUDY ¹

ÖRGÜTSEL ADALET İLE ÖRGÜTSEL GÜVEN ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİNİN TEST EDİLMESİ: BİR SAHA ÇALIŞMASI

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ABSTRACT

This research discusses the concept of organizational justice, its various dimensions, and its impact on individuals and institutions. It also demonstrates the importance of organizational trust in building strong relationships and achieving goals. This field study examines the perceptions of administrative employees at the University of Djelfa (Algeria) faculties regarding the impact of organizational justice on trust. Moreover, the study used descriptive and field study methods to achieve this goal. It included a sample of 194 employees. This study indicated that employees' perceptions of organizational justice and trust were average. The positive relationship between organizational justice and trust was confirmed. The procedural justice dimension has a strong relationship with organizational trust. At the same time, we did not find a significant relationship between "distributive justice" or "transactional justice" and organizational trust. In this research, we proposed enhancing trust and teamwork, organizing scientific seminars to raise awareness of the importance of organizational trust, studying the cultural and social factors that affect individuals' perceptions of justice and trust, adopting transparency and digitization, and fostering joint interactions between leaders and employees through direct communication and the regular sharing of important information.

Keywords: organizational trust, organizational justice, organizational behavior, impact.

ÖZ

Bu araştırma, örgütsel adalet kavramını, çeşitli boyutlarını ve bireyler ile kurumlar üzerindeki etkilerini ele almakta; aynı zamanda güçlü ilişkiler kurma ve kurumsal hedeflere ulaşmada örgütsel güvenin önemini vurgulamaktadır. Cezayir'deki Djelfa Üniversitesi fakültelerinde görev yapan idari personel üzerinde gerçekleştirilen saha çalışmasında, örgütsel adaletin güven üzerindeki etkisine ilişkin algılar incelenmiştir. Bu amaçla tanımlayıcı ve saha araştırması yöntemleri kullanılmış; 194 çalışandan oluşan bir örneklem araştırmaya dâhil edilmiştir. Bulgular, çalışanların örgütsel adalet ve güven algılarının genel olarak orta düzeyde olduğunu ve aralarında pozitif bir ilişki bulunduğunu göstermektedir. Özellikle işlemsel (prosedürel) adalet boyutunun güvenle güçlü bir ilişki içinde olduğu belirlenmiş, buna karşılık dağıtımsal ve etkileşimsel adalet boyutlarıyla güven arasında anlamlı bir ilişki tespit edilememiştir. Araştırma kapsamında, örgütsel güveni ve ekip çalışmasını artırmak amacıyla; güvenin önemi konusunda farkındalık yaratacak seminerlerin düzenlenmesi, adalet ve güven algılarını etkileyen kültürel ve sosyal faktörlerin araştırılması, şeffaflık ve dijitalleşmenin benimsenmesi, liderlerle çalışanlar arasında doğrudan iletişimin güçlendirilmesi ve bilgilerin düzenli paylaşımı yoluyla karşılıklı etkileşimin teşvik edilmesi önerilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: örgütsel güven, örgütsel adalet, örgütsel davranış, etki.

¹ The first author's doctoral thesis served as the basis for this article.

1. Introduction:

Human resources play a vital role in any organization. They are crucial in managing all activities and transforming inputs into outputs. Although an organization consists of several components, such as businesses, activities, available material resources, machinery, and equipment, human resources remain the most important. Its success or failure depends largely on the competence of its human resources and how they are managed and motivated to perform the required tasks effectively.

In the Algerian context, applying justice and the values of integrity and impartiality are essential for shaping positive behaviors and attitudes among employees in organizations. Organizational justice is regarded as one of the most important indicators that explain various values related to work and organizational behavior. The organizational justice theory, developed by Stacy Adams, is based on the principle of equality, whereby individuals feel satisfied when treated fairly in the workplace. This theory includes three types of justice: distributive, procedural, and interactional. Distributive justice relates to the equal distribution of rewards and benefits, while procedural justice relates to the fairness of organizational policies and procedures. Interactional justice relates to the fair treatment of all individuals. In addition to justice, organizational trust is pivotal in enhancing organizations' effectiveness and achieving their goals. Trust enhances cooperation and partnership between employees and management, which contributes to achieving organizational goals more efficiently. It allows employees to express their thoughts and feelings cooperatively, reduces conflicts, and increases organizational belonging, enhancing a positive and productive work environment.

Achieving justice and building trust among employees is one of the challenges facing Algerian universities, given the diversity of their human resources and the differences in their cultures, cognitive backgrounds, and economies. Considering that the University of Djelfa is one of the universities facing these challenges, this research will attempt to shed light on the concepts of organizational justice and organizational trust and analyze the relationship between them. This research will measure the attitudes of various administrative staff at the University of Djelfa's faculties regarding the relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust among employees.

1.1. Research Topic Objectives:

This study investigates the relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust among administrative staff at the faculties of the University of Djelfa. It uses tools like questionnaires and advanced statistical methods (e.g., Smart-PLS). Subobjectives include identifying key components of justice and trust by reviewing previous research and relevant theories, such as justice theory and social exchange theory. The study also aims to offer data-driven recommendations to raise employee awareness of organizational justice and improve trust, supported by case study examples and analysis of potential impacts. It is also helpful for researchers interested in this field.

1.2. Significance of the Research Topic:

The research holds both academic and practical importance. Academically, it is how organizational justice influences trust, fills gaps in current literature, and supports the development of management concepts and institutional performance. Practically, it helps

faculty administrations at the University of Djelfa improve administrative practices by identifying strengths and weaknesses in justice and trust and suggesting ways to improve. The research can lead to a better work environment, reduced stress, increased collaboration and innovation, and improved overall performance. It also promotes employee motivation, loyalty, and lower turnover, helping the university meet its goals. The findings may serve as a model for other academic institutions seeking to enhance justice, trust, and performance.

1.3. Research Problems and Questions:

The research addresses the effect of organizational justice on organizational trust, a key issue in understanding workplace dynamics. Different types of justice (distributive, procedural, and interactional) significantly affect employee satisfaction and behavior. Fairness fosters loyalty and performance, while perceived injustice reduces motivation and engagement. Trust is essential for strong workplace relationships, better communication, and innovation. Although building trust is challenging, leadership plays a critical role in creating a fair and supportive environment. The study aims to answer the central question:

To what extent does organizational justice influence organizational trust among administrative staff at the faculties of the University of Djelfa?

Based on this problem, the research seeks answers to the following subquestions:

- What is the relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa?
- What is the nature of the relationship between distributive justice and organizational trust among administrative staff at the faculties of the University of Djelfa?
- What is the nature of the relationship between procedural justice and organizational trust among administrative staff at the faculties of the University of Djelfa?
- What is the nature of the relationship between interactional justice and organizational trust among administrative staff at the faculties of the University of Djelfa?

1.4. Research Hypotheses:

To answer the study's problem and questions, we will formulate research hypotheses and attempt to test their validity statistically. The research hypotheses are listed below:

- The first primary hypothesis, H₁: There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between organizational justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa.
- The first sub-hypothesis, H₁₋₁: There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between distributive justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa.
- The second sub-hypothesis, H₁₋₂: There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between procedural justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa.
- The third hypothesis, H₁₋₃: There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between interactional justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa.

1.5. Research Model:

This model examines the impact of organizational justice as an independent variable on organizational trust among employees by analyzing its dimensions and their impact on organizational trust.

Figure 1

Research Model

Source: Prepared by the researchers, based on previous research. We denote the hypothesis as H₁.

1.6. Research Limits

This study is limited to examining the relationship between organizational justice in its three dimensions (distributive, procedural, and interactional) and organizational trust in its various forms (trust in colleagues, supervisors, and management). It also includes other variables to help get a better grasp of employee behavior. Spatially, the research is conducted within the faculties of the University of Djelfa, with the possibility of comparing results to similar studies at other universities. The study focuses on a random sample of 372 administrative employees, using qualitative interviews to support quantitative findings. Temporally, the research takes place in early 2025, considering seasonal factors and university events to ensure accuracy. Although these limits may affect the generalizability of the results, they provide an appropriate framework for studying the impact of organizational justice on trust within the university context.

1.7. Research Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive approach to examine the relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust within the faculties of the University of Djelfa. It combines both quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure a well-rounded analysis. Data will be collected through questionnaires and interviews and then analyzed using regression and path analysis to explore how organizational justice influences trust. Quantitative data will be processed using statistical programs such as SPSS and Smart-PLS, while qualitative data will undergo content analysis to deepen understanding of the topic and ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

1.8. Previous Research

Several studies have examined how perceptions of organizational justice affect trust. Solinas-Saunders et al. (2024) found that procedural and interactional justice rather than distributive justice predict employee trust in correctional institutions (Solinas-Saunders et al., 2024). Bidarian and Jafari (2012) reported a positive link between justice and trust at a Tehran university (Bidarian & Jafari, 2012). Hubbell and Chory-Assad (2005) found that procedural justice was the strongest predictor of organizational and managerial trust (Hubbell & Chory-Assad, 2005). Saunders & Thornhill (2004) explored the coexistence of trust and distrust during organizational change, showing that justice perceptions help explain these dynamics (Saunders & Thornhill, 2004).

1.9. Value of Previous Research

These studies confirm the key role of justice in building trust, shaping employee behavior, and strengthening organizational outcomes. They also provide a solid theoretical base for this study, informing the research model, survey design, and choice of statistical tools. They enable meaningful comparisons and highlight gaps this study aims to fill.

1.10. What Distinguishes This Research

This study combines quantitative and qualitative methods to examine organizational justice and trust in depth. It uses Smart-PLS for advanced analysis and gathers insights through surveys and interviews with staff at the University of Djelfa. By grounding the research in recent literature and applying it to a specific academic setting, the study delivers new insights, addresses knowledge gaps, and offers practical recommendations, contributing significantly to the field.

2. Conceptual implications of the research variables

Organizational justice is a key factor influencing organizational behavior, as it is closely linked to various organizational variables that significantly contribute to success and development. Recognized as a fundamental determinant of behavior within organizations, it has attracted the attention of researchers in organizational behavior and management, who consider it essential for organizational effectiveness. Therefore, understanding and applying the concept of organizational justice is vital to ensuring the sustainability and adaptability of organizations in a dynamic and evolving business environment.

2.1. Origins and Evolution of Organizational Justice in Management Thought

The concept of organizational justice has evolved through several key contributions to management thought. It began with Adams' equity theory in the 1960s, who introduced distributive justice through equity theory, emphasizing fairness in the ratio of an individual's inputs (e.g., effort, experience) to their outcomes compared to others (Adams, 1963). Later, in 1975, Thibaut and Walker introduced procedural justice, asserting that people perceive outcomes as fair when they are involved in the decision-making process. They highlighted the importance of process control in achieving fairness (Thibaut & Walker, 1975). Building on this, Leventhal (1980) proposed six rules for procedural justice: consistency, bias suppression, accuracy, correctability, representativeness, and ethicality—forming the basis for many later studies (Leventhal, 1980). In 1986, interactional justice was introduced by Bies and Moag, focusing on fairness in interpersonal interactions and communication, including

the respectful and honest treatment of employees (Bies & Moag, 1986). This dimension addressed the social and relational aspects of justice within organizations. Together, these three dimensions—distributive, procedural, and interactional—form a comprehensive understanding of organizational justice. Their development reflects a growing recognition of justice as a key driver of employee attitudes, behaviors, and organizational effectiveness, making it a central concern in organizational behavior and management research.

2.2. The Concept of Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is a central concept in management and social studies. It is defined in various ways by different thinkers. Here are some basic definitions of the concept:

Greenberg (1987) proposed that organizational justice depends on dimensions related to human interaction. Greenberg classified these dimensions into immediate and proactive reactions, which include distributive, procedural, and interactional justice (Greenberg, 1987). Colquitt stated that organizational justice is assessed using four key areas: distributive justice (fairness in how resources are shared), procedural justice (fairness in the processes used), interactional justice (how people are treated), and informational justice (how decisions are communicated) (Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng, 2001). Organizational justice is defined by Cropanzano et al. (2007) as the organization's ability to achieve substantial benefits for employees and the organization by enhancing trust, commitment, and job performance. It also includes procedures such as hiring, performance appraisal, and reward systems (Cropanzano, Bowen, & Gilliland, 2007). According to Wiseman and Stillwell (2022), organizational justice is individuals' perceptions of fair or unfair treatment within organizations. This perception includes decisions regarding resource allocation and interpersonal interactions by managers. Organizational justice is classified into four main dimensions: distributive, procedural, interactional, and informational. These dimensions significantly impact employee satisfaction, trust, and performance, while low levels of justice lead to increased negative behaviors, such as absenteeism and aggression (Wiseman & Stillwell, 2022).

Organizational justice means how fair employees think their organization is when it comes to sharing resources and rewards (distributive justice), the fairness of the rules and processes used (procedural justice), and the fairness of how people treat each other in the organization (interactional justice). Distributive justice is how resources and rewards are allocated among workers and how fair they think it is. Procedural justice relates to the fairness and transparency of the processes and procedures used in decision-making. Interactional justice is how people in an organization treat and respect each other. Organizational justice also reflects employees' sense that they are treated fairly and transparently in all aspects of their work.

2.3. Effects of Organizational Justice

Organizational justice plays an important role in organizations, contributing to achieving numerous goals and benefits. The absence of organizational justice can result in a multitude of negative consequences, summarized as follows: Organizational justice has a profound impact on both individual and organizational outcomes. When correctly applied, it brings numerous positive effects. It enhances organizational trust and commitment, improves employee performance, and strengthens relationships between employees and their

supervisors, as well as with the organization itself. Fair treatment fosters positive behaviors, such as increased job satisfaction and organizational loyalty, while reducing turnover intentions. Research has shown that perceptions of fairness are linked to greater satisfaction and higher motivation (Cropanzano, Byrne, Bobocel, & Rupp, 2001). According to Greenberg (1990), organizational justice also boosts employees' self-worth, shows appreciation for their contributions, and reinforces ethical values within the organization (Greenberg, 1990).

Conversely, from our perspective on organizational justice, the absence of organizational justice can lead to harmful consequences. Employees who perceive injustice may become disengaged or even hostile. When ambitious employees are denied fair opportunities, they may either leave the organization or retaliate by engaging in harmful actions such as reducing their work effort, mistreating customers, leaking sensitive information, or damaging the organization's reputation. These behaviors threaten the organization's performance and public image. Hence, institutions need to build transparent and fair systems that support employee trust and engagement. Ensuring justice in decision-making and resource allocation not only fosters a positive work environment but also contributes to long-term organizational success and stability.

2.4. Dimensions of Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is a pivotal concept in the contemporary workplace. It has three main dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. These dimensions aim to ensure a sense of fairness among employees, which is reflected in job performance, satisfaction, and organizational loyalty.

A. *Distributive Justice:* Distributive justice focuses on the fairness of the distribution of resources and rewards within an organization, such as wages, incentives, and promotions. It is primarily linked to Adams's (1963) equity theory, whereby an employee evaluates his effort against the rewards he receives compared to his colleagues. Distributive justice includes three main patterns: distribution according to performance (alternative justice), according to need (contingent justice), or equally among all ("egalitarian justice") (Adams, 1963). It is based on three basic rules, as defined by Organ (1988): the equality rule, which requires rewarding an individual based on the effort expended; the quality rule, which calls for distribution without personal discrimination; and the need rule, which favors individuals with greater need when conditions are equal (Organ, 1988). The ways to judge fairness in rewards include the merit standard, which gives rewards based on how well someone performs; the equality standard, which distributes rewards equally no matter the effort; and the job status standard, which gives bigger rewards to people in higher positions (Leventhal, 1980). Organizations struggle with making this fairness work, especially when balancing equality and fairness, being open about how rewards are given, and dealing with different cultural norms in different organizations (Greenberg, 1990). To illustrate how distributive justice is applied in practice, some practical examples from well-known organizations can be used. Transparency in the distribution of wages and benefits is an essential part of Google's corporate culture. The company sets clear standards for evaluating performance and determining rewards, which enhances employees' sense of fairness. Google also relies on fairness standards to evaluate performance and distribute rewards based on employees' contributions to achieving company goals (Brock, 2015).

B. Procedural Justice: Procedural justice refers to the integrity and fairness of the procedures followed in making decisions related to the distribution of resources within organizations, such as promotion mechanisms or performance evaluations. Employees feel treated fairly when the processes are clear, consistent, and unbiased (Thibaut & Walker, 1975). Leventhal identified a set of rules to ensure procedural fairness: the possibility of appeal, impartiality, ethics, accuracy, representativeness, and consistency (Leventhal, 1980). Greenberg and Baron classified procedural justice into two basic dimensions: the social dimension, which focuses on the quality of interaction and communication with the employee, and the structural dimension, which reflects the transparency and objectivity of the procedures followed (Greenberg & Baron, 1997). Procedural justice is evaluated according to several criteria, including the consistency of standards, gathering accurate information, involving employees in decision-making, explaining the justifications for decisions made, and providing additional information upon request (Folger & Konovsky, 1989). However, implementing procedural justice faces several challenges, such as poor transparency, limited employee participation in decisions, and a lack of training for managers on the principles of fair decision-making. Furthermore, the difficulty of reconciling the achievement of justice with prompt decision-making is also evident. To illustrate how procedural justice is applied in practice, some practical examples from well-known organizations can be used. Intel applies procedural justice through transparent performance evaluation and promotion policies, allowing employees to voice their opinions and participate in decision-making. The company ensures that all evaluation criteria are known and procedures are transparent and fair (Intel, 2024). At Microsoft, procedural justice rules are implemented to ensure employee participation in decision-making and provide channels for grievances and appeals. The company uses transparent and clear evaluation systems to ensure fair processes (Microsoft, 2024).

C. Interactional Justice: Interactional justice refers to the quality of treatment employees receive from their supervisors in the workplace. It includes elements of respect, appreciation, and transparency during personal interactions. It is the human extension of procedural justice (Bies & Moag, 1986). Interactional justice is influenced by several factors, including clear justification for decisions made, openness and sincerity in communication, politeness and respect in dealings, and appreciation of employee needs when implementing decisions. Moorman and Niehoff identified a set of basic criteria for this justice: mutual respect, clarity and transparency, logical justification for decisions, and mutual trust between employee and supervisor (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993). Interactional justice positively impacts job satisfaction, a sense of belonging, and the desire to continue working. However, low interactional justice may lead to increased levels of stress and an increased likelihood of withdrawal or resignation from the job (Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng, 2001).

The three dimensions interconnect. Perceptions of distributive justice often depend on the procedures' fairness. Interactional justice encompasses implementing these procedures and the level of respect they offer. Thus, each dimension influences the others, and the failure of one may weaken organizational justice as a whole.

3. The General Framework of Organizational Trust

Organizational trust is a key element in modern institutions. It plays a crucial role in strengthening internal relationships, supporting strategic decisions, and promoting positive employee behaviors. It fosters collaboration and commitment and helps organizations effectively achieve their goals.

3.1. The origins and development of the concept of organizational trust

The concept of organizational trust has deep philosophical roots, with Hobbes emphasizing the social contract to avoid chaos (Baumgold, 2013). Moreover, Locke viewed trust as fundamental for legitimate governance and cooperation (Newton, 2001). Durkheim further highlighted trust's role in societal stability (Hupcey, Penrod, Morse, & Mitcham, 2001). Early organizational theories by Taylor and Weber focused more on authority and formal systems, largely ignoring trust (Hosmer, 1995). This focus shifted with the human relations school, where Barnard stressed that organizational cooperation depends on trust (Barnard, 1968). Mid-20th-century psychological studies connected trust to healthy development and everyday interactions (Erikson, 1963). Luhmann later noted that trust reduces social complexity, facilitating organizational interactions (Luhmann, 2018). In the 1980s, trust gained attention in leadership and change management, linked to loyalty through models like Theory Z (Ouchi & Price, 1978). By the 1990s, trust was associated with social capital and resilience, vital for collaboration in evolving workplaces (Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995). Entering the 21st century, organizational trust became key for enhancing communication, fostering innovation, and easing change amid globalization and technological advances (Newell & Swan, 2000), making it crucial for organizational stability and adaptability today.

3.2. The Concept of Organizational Trust

Organizational trust is a key concept in studying organizational behavior and managing relationships. It is a multidimensional concept that overlaps with various fields, such as psychology, economics, and sociology. For example, Ellen's definition of organizational trust emphasizes the importance of trust in employee-employer relationships. It considers trust to be linked to transparency and commitment on the part of the leader (Ellen, 1997). However, this definition may be limited in its coverage of other organizational relationships, such as trust between colleagues or employees and top management. Tyler et al. focused on trust as a prerequisite for compliance with rules and risk-taking, reflecting a broader perspective (Tyler, Callahan, & Frost, 2007) but potentially ignoring the emotional and moral aspects crucial to building organizational trust.

On the other hand, other definitions focus on the belief in the reliability of specific individuals based on their expected behavior, such as colleagues, direct supervisors, or senior management, as well as the lack of attention to oversight (Hoy & Tschannen-Moran, 1999). However, the broad description of these behaviors may not provide specific guidance for enhancing trust within organizations. Some view organizational trust as a rational act facilitated by social structures. It is also an emotional process reinforced by the perceived reliability of the trusted group and the faith of the individuals who offer their trust. That is, its existence is implicitly assumed to enhance the expected outcomes of the relationship (Ashu et al., 2019). This assumption does not always guarantee positive or beneficial actions

or behaviors for group members. Individuals may believe that others will behave in specific ways, even if these actions are undesirable and shameful. Trust is a rational decision based on calculating benefits and risks and a complex process that includes emotions, experiences, and group interactions (Di Battista, Pivetti, & Berti, 2020).

Thus, we conclude that organizational trust is people's faith in their workplace, leaders, and coworkers. It reflects how employees believe their organization will act with integrity and fairness and honor its commitments to them. It is also essential for enhancing cooperation and job performance and facilitating the achievement of shared goals. Organizational policies and practices that reflect transparency, integrity, efficiency, and fairness build this trust.

3.3. Effects of Organizational Trust

Organizational trust enhances job security, motivation, and participation in achieving goals (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). It promotes honest communication, clear roles, and stronger decision-making (Kramer, 1999). Trust improves workplace relationships and job satisfaction and supports delegation and development when evaluation is fair (Judge & Bono, 2001). It boosts leadership effectiveness, risk management, resource use, and organizational credibility (Edmondson, 1999). In contrast, low trust reduces motivation, weakens commitment, and harms teamwork (Cameron, 2011). It leads to poor communication, blocks innovation, and increases control needs. This creates a rigid, tense environment with delays, conflict, and defensive behavior (McAllister, 2017).

3.4. Dimensions of Organizational Trust

Organizational trust is a fundamental concept in understanding the dynamics of relationships within the workplace. Many researchers have focused on analyzing it through three main dimensions: trust in colleagues, trust in supervisors, and trust in top management. These interconnected dimensions are crucial in enhancing collective and individual performance within organizations. They also form a framework for understanding individual behavior and interactions in the workplace. The following is a summary of these dimensions:

- **A. Trust among colleagues:** Trust is the cornerstone of building effective and productive teams. Collaborative relationships built on respect and trust enhance team performance and facilitate knowledge sharing (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). This trust depends on several components: a commitment to cooperation, fulfilling promises, and organizational justice, which makes individuals feel that their rights are protected and their contributions are fairly valued. An effective knowledge management system enables team members to exchange skills and expertise, increasing teamwork efficiency. Power dynamics within a team also directly impact trust. A fair distribution of power promotes transparency and reduces conflict, whereas the authoritarian use of power undermines trust and reduces the effectiveness of collaboration (Panteli & Tucker, 2009). Furthermore, trust is affected by organizational factors such as policy changes and organizational culture, which requires management to establish a culture that encourages cooperation and fairness to ensure trust sustainability (Brion, Mo, & Lount Jr., 2019).

- **B. Trust in supervisors:** Trust in supervisors is vital to team cohesion and professional relationships. Employees build trust based on the supervisor's competence, integrity, and openness. A successful supervisor must be competent in technical aspects and leadership

skills such as conflict management and effective communication (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). Ethical integrity is also the basis for building trust, as a supervisor's fair and transparent actions enhance employees' feelings of security and respect (Chughtai, Byrne, & Flood, 2015). In addition, a supervisor's ability to listen to their employees and offer necessary support plays an important role in establishing a positive relationship (Nienaber, Romeike, Searle, & Schewe, 2015). The organizational environment also affects the extent to which employees trust their supervisors. The implementation of equitable and transparent policies enhances trust. At the same time, ambiguity or bias leads to its erosion (Wu, Huang, Li, & Liu, 2012). Trust in the supervisor is determined by three basic elements: a tendency toward goodness, professional competence, and integrity. In conjunction with an equitable work environment and a supervisor who demonstrates competence and equilibrium, these factors lead to successful leadership and strong trust from subordinates (Akram et al., 2018).

- **C. Trust in Top Management:** Trust in top management is crucial in building a favorable organizational climate that enhances productivity and corporate loyalty. This trust is evident when employees feel that leadership decisions are fair and transparent and that there is genuine concern for their needs and aspirations. This trust is greatly enhanced when management is committed to fulfilling its promises and matching its words with its actions, especially in developing the professional environment and providing material and moral support (Dirks & Ferrin, 2002). Organizational justice, particularly in resource allocation and decision-making processes, is a crucial foundation, as employees perceive themselves as integral to a fair business that supports and cherishes them (Greenberg, 1990). In addition, management that invests in employee career development and provides growth opportunities enhances employee trust and creates a stable work environment. The transparent organizational culture adopted by leadership also affects employee perceptions, as the consistency of values between what the organization declares and what it practices increases management's credibility (Kramer, 1999). However, if trust declines, it could lead to declining loyalty, reduced performance, and increased employee turnover. Therefore, senior management must adopt policies based on transparency, fairness, and understanding employees' needs to ensure continued trust and support for the organization's success (Robinson, 1996).

4. Study Methods and Procedures

This section presents the methodological steps needed to conduct the study, from developing the instrument to determining the sample, collecting data, and statistically analyzing it to achieve the research objectives.

4.1. Developing the Study Tool:

A questionnaire was developed specifically for the current study. It included items to measure employees' perceptions of prevailing organizational justice and their trust in the college's management, leadership, and intentions. This questionnaire was designed using a five-point Likert scale and comprised 24 items, making it easy for employees to understand and complete. Ten expert reviewers from various international universities, selected for their specializations and experience in the research topic, reviewed the questionnaire. They were asked to provide their opinions on the questions' clarity, relevance to the research topic, and ease of completion. This process contributed to improving the structure of the questionnaire

and ensuring its clarity and relevance, which led to improved data quality, increased accuracy of results, and enhanced confidence in the study's validity.

4.2. Study Population and Sample:

The study targeted 372 administrative employees at the University of Djelfa. Using Thompson's equation, the required sample size was calculated as 189. To ensure accuracy and minimize error, 260 questionnaires were distributed, excluding those on extended leave. A total of 205 responses were received, with 194 valid for analysis—representing 52% of the population and exceeding the minimum required. The sample was proportionally distributed across the faculties, enhancing the representativeness and statistical reliability. It strengthened the study's validity and reduced the likelihood of random error.

4.3. Evaluating the Validity of the Standard Model:

To develop models that fit the research context better and have greater validity, researchers must ensure that these models possess high levels of validity and reliability. Achieving these criteria enables future studies to use these models efficiently. Hence, the importance of both convergent validity and discriminant validity becomes apparent. Therefore, the current study relied on these two types of tests to test the validity of the measurements.

Table 1

Standard Model Quality Standards

Variables	Dimensions	Items	FL	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
Organizational Justice	Distributive Justice	X11	0.427	0.727	0.833	0.570
		X12	0.780			
		X13	0.851			
		X14	0.874			
	Procedural Justice	X21	0.284 (delete)	0.625	0.786	0.508
		X22	0.701			
		X23	0.850			
		X24	0.858			
	Interactional Justice	X31	0.879	0.794	0.870	0.640
		X32	0.912			
X33		0.861				
X34		0.461				
Organizational Trust	Trust in Colleagues	Y11	0.627	0.714	0.821	0.537
		Y12	0.771			
		Y13	0.719			
		Y14	0.801			
	Trust in Supervisor	Y21	0.408 (delete)	0.653	0.799	0.512
		Y22	0.785			
		Y23	0.768			
		Y24	0.823			
	Trust in University Leadership	Y31	0.892	0.813	0.881	0.657
		Y32	0.905			
Y33		0.859				
Y34		0.525				

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

According to Table, some of Cronbach's alpha internal consistency scores are below 0.7, showing that the study tool lacks the needed reliability, meaning the data might be unreliable and unsuitable for final analysis. Remove items from the questionnaire to improve reliability and make the data consistent with the expected model. These changes will enhance measurement quality and lead to better interpretation of the results based on the remaining

data. It is concluded that it is necessary to delete the confusing items from the questionnaire to ensure improved stability and reliability and increase the consistency of the data with the hypothesized model so that the quality of measurement is improved and the results are better interpreted based on the remaining data. The table below shows how we checked the model's validity after taking out the confusing items, pointing out the better stability and reliability indicators (like composite reliability and average variance extracted) and the consistency of the remaining data.

Table 2

Measurement model quality criteria after removing confounding items

Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Distributive Justice	0.727	0.833	0.570
Procedural Justice	0.752	0.859	0.672
Interactional Justice	0.794	0.870	0.639
Trust in Colleagues	0.714	0.818	0.532
Trust in Supervisor	0.760	0.862	0.676
Trust in University Leadership	0.813	0.881	0.657

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The table below shows the validity criteria for the standard model after removing the confounding items. We note that the average expected values (AVE) range between 0.532 and 0.676. These values indicate that all scale dimensions fall within the acceptable range of 0.5. It means that the average values of the items in each dimension are relatively high, indicating a high quality of interpretation. The composite reliability coefficients (CR) range between 0.818 and 0.881. These values indicate that the internal consistency of the scales is relatively high, as they all fall above 0.7. This value indicates that each dimension's items exhibit interrelatedness and provide a consistent and accurate measure of the concept. All Cronbach's alpha coefficients range between 0.714 and 0.813. These values indicate that the internal consistency of the scales remains high after removing any item that might negatively affect the scale. It means that the scale is robust and stable, even after removing any item that might be inconsistent. These results validate the standard model's validity and reliability, demonstrating its ability to assess organizational justice and trust concepts accurately.

4.4. Evaluating the evidence of discriminant validity:

Key statistical methods are used to assess discriminant validity, particularly the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the HTMT ratio, as well as the variance inflation factor (VIF) and cross-loading indices (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019). The following tables present the results:

A. Cross-Loading Test: The following table shows the cross-loading fit indices test results, which assess the extent to which items fit with their respective variables compared to other variables.

Table 3

Cross-Loading Fit Indices

	Distributive Justice	Procedural Justice	Interactional Justice	Trust in Colleagues	Trust in Supervisor	Trust in University Leadership
X11	0.424	0.114	0.139	0.190	-0.011	0.028
X12	0.774	0.317	0.156	0.309	0.018	0.072
X13	0.856	0.422	0.029	0.243	0.188	0.192
X14	0.877	0.444	0.077	0.167	0.096	0.215
X22	0.349	0.717	0.355	0.383	0.211	0.250
X23	0.424	0.860	0.398	0.292	0.401	0.196
X24	0.351	0.873	0.455	0.094	0.154	0.132
X31	0.097	0.472	0.881	0.300	0.107	0.061
X32	0.119	0.451	0.912	0.300	0.173	0.120
X33	0.132	0.383	0.863	0.243	0.133	0.012
X34	-0.002	0.228	0.454	0.139	-0.059	-0.005
Y11	-0.002	0.024	0.384	0.599	0.247	-0.084
Y12	0.210	0.216	0.307	0.757	0.208	0.108
Y13	0.382	0.398	0.224	0.747	0.475	0.310
Y14	0.156	0.133	0.076	0.798	0.304	0.039
Y22	0.177	0.350	0.123	0.468	0.808	0.176
Y23	-0.076	0.066	0.187	0.356	0.775	0.012
Y24	0.134	0.317	0.041	0.280	0.879	0.341
Y31	0.113	0.213	0.101	0.233	0.191	0.891
Y32	0.102	0.155	0.060	0.123	0.210	0.906
Y33	0.196	0.148	0.037	0.109	0.211	0.859
Y34	0.234	0.280	-0.001	0.060	0.129	0.526

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

Cross-loading indices confirm that each item is more closely related to its construct than any other latent variable. This assessment helps ensure the distinctiveness of items and enhances the accuracy of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model. A cross-loading value above 0.50 is generally considered strong and indicative of excellent item reliability. Conversely, values below 0.40 are viewed as weak and may require reevaluation or item revision. (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). The indices demonstrate excellent fit when the item loads higher on its variable than on other variables, meaning that each latent variable is measured only through its statements without interference with other variables.

B. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test: This tool evaluates a structural model by measuring the degree of multicollinearity between the independent variables. This tool helps address the problem of collinearity between the model components. A VIF value is considered acceptable if it ranges between 1 and 5. This level of agreement indicates a moderate relationship between the predictor variables. Values exceeding 5 indicate a serious problem with multicollinearity, which may require deleting some questionnaire items (Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2021). The following table shows the results of the VIF test. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) addresses the collinearity problem between standard model factors.

Table 4

Variance inflation factors

	Items	VIF	Items	VIF	Items	VIF	Items	VIF
Distributive Justice	X11	1.108	X12	1.693	X13	2.772	Z14	2.630
Procedural Justice	X21	/	X22	1.470	X23	2.382	Z24	2.959
Interactional Justice	X31	2.254	X32	3.292	X33	3.006	Z34	1.174
Trust in Colleagues	Y11	1.605	Y12	1.933	Y13	1.636	Z14	1.607
Trust in Supervisor	Y21	/	Y22	1.439	Y23	1.575	Z24	1.879
Trust in University Leadership	Y31	2.386	Y32	3.192	Y33	2.662	Z34	1.222

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The results of the previous table indicate that all VIF values are less than 5, meaning there is no excessive linear correlation between the factors in the model and that the variables are independent. Such an outcome enhances the model's reliability and ability to explain the relationships between independent and dependent variables, thereby supporting the validity of the analysis.

C. HTMT Test: The Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) assesses discriminant validity by measuring how distinct latent variables are. A model demonstrates good discriminant validity if most HTMT values are below 0.85, though in some cases, a threshold of 0.90 may be acceptable. Values above 0.85 indicate potential overlap between constructs, suggesting the need to revise or remove ambiguous survey items to improve the model (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015).

Table 5

Overlap of dimensions according to the HTMT test

	Trust in Colleagues	Trust in University Leadership.	Trust in Supervisor	Procedural Justice.	Distributive Justice.	Interactional Justice.
Trust in Colleagues.						
Trust in University Leadership.	0.257					
Trust in Supervisor.	0.575	0.280				
Procedural Justice.	0.383	0.324	0.421			
Distributive Justice.	0.419	0.259	0.213	0.605		
Interactional Justice.	0.464	0.103	0.257	0.631	0.195	

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

According to the table, all values of the congruence coefficient between the variables are less than the minimum value specified at 0.85. The current study model has achieved discriminant validity, demonstrating adequate structural discrimination between the variables.

D. Fornell-Larcker: The Fornell-Larcker criterion evaluates discriminant validity by verifying that each latent construct is distinct from others. This is confirmed when the square root of a construct's Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is greater than its correlations with other constructs, indicating that the construct explains more variance in its indicators than it shares with others (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 6

Overlap of dimensions with each other, according to the Fornell-Larker test

	Trust in Colleagues	Trust in University Leadership	Trust in Supervisor	Procedural Justice	Distributive Justice	Interactional Justice
Trust in Colleagues	0.729					
Trust in University Leadership	0.171	0.811				
Trust in Supervisor	0.446	0.231	0.822			
Procedural Justice	0.304	0.231	0.313	0.820		
Distributive Justice	0.296	0.184	0.110	0.458	0.755	
Interactional Justice	0.317	0.068	0.135	0.493	0.121	0.800

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The numbers on the diagonal of the matrix, which show the square roots of the AVE, are greater than the correlations between the other latent variables, confirming that each construct represents a different idea. This result indicates that the model demonstrates excellent discriminant validity, as the constructs are sufficiently distinct. The high diagonal values reflect strong differentiation among the dimensions. Furthermore, the observed correlations between constructs are moderate to low, suggesting minimal overlap and supporting the constructs' independence. This level of differentiation is crucial for ensuring the model's effectiveness in measuring distinct theoretical concepts. In summary, the Fornell-Larcker test results indicate that the model exhibits high discriminant validity, with only minor, acceptable overlaps that do not compromise its overall validity.

4.5. Evaluating the Study's Structural Model:

After evaluating the measurement model, we must move on to evaluating the overall results of the model through

A. Coefficient of Determination (R^2): According to Chin (1998), the coefficient of determination (R^2) reflects the predictive accuracy of the structural model in SEM. It indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. An R^2 value above 0.67 suggests a substantial predictive power; values between 0.33 and 0.67 indicate a moderate effect, while values below 0.33 reflect a weak explanatory power (Chin, 1998).

Table 7

Coefficient of Determination (R-Square)

Variable	R^2	R^2 Adjusted
Organizational Trust	0.164	0.159

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The adjusted and unadjusted coefficients of the determination indicate that the regression model can explain the behavior of the dependent variable, "organizational trust." The independent variable, organizational justice, explains and accounts for 16% of the variance in the dependent variable, organizational trust. However, we consider this a weak percentage because it is less than 33%. We also note that the adjusted determination value is close to and does not differ significantly from the determination values, indicating the model's quality and significance.

B. Effect Size F^2 : Effect size F^2 complements the coefficient of determination by measuring each independent variable's unique contribution to the model's explanatory power (Baron & Kenny, 1986). According to Cohen's (1988) classification, an F^2 greater than 0.35 indicates a significant effect, between 0.15 and 0.35 a medium effect, between 0.02 and 0.15 a small effect, and below 0.02 suggests no meaningful effect (Cohen, 1988).

Table 8

Effect Size F^2

Variable	Value	Effect Size
Organizational Justice → Organizational Trust	0.196	Medium

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The results showed a moderate relationship between organizational justice and trust, with a value of 19%. Based on these results, we conclude that there is a positive relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust.

4.6. Testing the Study Hypotheses:

The study hypotheses are tested using path analysis combined with the bootstrap technique. Following Hayes and Preacher, relationships between variables are assessed through P-values, which represent the likelihood of error in the observed relationship. A P-value below 0.05 indicates a significant relationship. Additionally, the beta coefficient is derived from the original sample: a positive beta indicates a direct correlation, while a negative beta indicates an inverse correlation (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2013). The central hypothesis H₁ and sub-hypotheses are tested: "There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between organizational justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa." The examination is done using the results of the two models and the following table:

Figure 2

Model for testing the primary hypothesis H₁

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

Figure 3

Model for testing the sub-hypotheses of the central hypothesis H₁

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

The following table shows the results of testing the second hypothesis of the research and its sub-hypotheses, which aim to verify the existence of a positive relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust.

Table 9

Results for testing the primary hypothesis H₁ and its sub-hypotheses

Path	Regression Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
Organizational Justice → → Organizational Trust.	0.405	0.064	6.286	0.000	Accept hypothesis H ₁ .
Distributive Justice → → Organizational Trust.	0.107	0.069	1.540	0.124	Reject hypothesis H ₁₋₁ .
Procedural Justice → → Organizational Trust.	0.365	0.068	5.370	0.000	Accept hypothesis H ₁₋₂ .
Interactional Justice → → Organizational Trust.	0.063	0.072	0.875	0.381	Reject hypothesis H ₁₋₃ .

Source: Prepared by researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program Smart-PLS.V: 4.4.

- **Organizational Justice and Organizational Trust:** The positive regression coefficient of 0.405 indicates a positive relationship between organizational justice and trust. The T value of 6,286 was greater than the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05. Moreover, the p-value was less than the significance level of 0.05. Reaching 0.000. The finding supports the acceptance of the central hypothesis H₁: "There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between organizational justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa." This result is consistent with studies by (Chen et al., 2015) and (Bidarian & Jafari, 2012).

- **Distributive justice—Organizational Trust:** The P value was greater than the significance level of 0.05, reaching 0.124, which supports the rejection of sub-hypothesis H₁₋₁, which states, "There is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between distributive justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa." This result differs from the study (Bidarian & Jafari, 2012), the study (Solinas-Saunders et al., 2024), and (Hubbell & Chory-Assad, 2005).

- **Procedural Justice—Organizational Trust:** The positive regression coefficient of 0.365 indicates a positive relationship between procedural justice and organizational trust. The T value of 5,370 was greater than the critical value of 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05, and the P value was less than the significance level of 0.05. Reaching 0.000. This evidence supports the idea that "there is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between procedural justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa." This result is consistent with the study (Hubbell & Chory-Assad, 2005), the study (Chen et al., 2015), and the study (Solinas-Saunders et al., 2024).

- **Transactional fairness—Organizational Trust:** The p-value was greater than the significance level of 0.05, reaching 0.381. This result supports rejecting the sub-hypothesis H₁₋₃, which says that "there is a statistically significant positive relationship at a 5% significance level between interactional justice and organizational trust among administrative employees at the faculties of the University of Djelfa." It differs from the

study (Solinas-Saunders et al., 2024), while this result agrees with the study (Hubbell & Chory-Assad, 2005).

4.7. Discussion of the results of testing the central hypothesis H₁ and its sub-hypotheses:

The results in the table support a positive relationship between organizational justice in general and organizational trust, as employees who feel they are treated fairly by their colleagues are more likely to trust them. This finding supports previous research that highlights the role of organizational justice in creating a positive work environment where employees can trust their colleagues and leaders. Remarkably, the relationship between the dimensions of justice and organizational trust was mixed. While the results showed a strong positive relationship between procedural justice and organizational trust, distributive justice and interactional justice did not show any statistically significant relationship with organizational trust. This disparity may be attributed to transactional justice related to employee experiences with colleagues.

In contrast, other factors, such as each college's general values and practices, can influence organizational trust. The results indicate the importance of building a fair and inclusive work environment to enhance employee and organization trust. Overall, we can interpret these results by considering the nature of the various justice dimensions. Organizational justice focuses on employees' general perceptions of the organization's fairness, while procedural justice focuses on the integrity of organizational procedures. The strong relationship between procedural justice and organizational trust can be explained by the theory of "reciprocity," as employees who are treated fairly in their procedures feel more confident in their organizations.

5. Conclusion

In the theoretical aspect of this research, we concluded that organizational justice is a central concept in management thought and has diverse impacts on individuals and organizations. Organizational justice encompasses several forms and dimensions, each requiring consideration of specific principles and models to achieve. Theories and studies demonstrate the importance of organizational justice in motivating individuals and enhancing their performance within organizations, as there is a positive relationship between it and job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Furthermore, organizational trust is essential in building and strengthening relationships. This trust is essential for achieving goals and enhancing performance. Several factors influence it and necessitate its conscious and deliberate development. Transparency and effective communication also enhance organizational trust, which positively impacts team performance and the effectiveness of teamwork. These trusts are essential for achieving organizational goals and fostering positive relationships among individuals within an organization.

5.1. Results of the applied aspect:

We can draw the following conclusions from our field study at the University of Djelfa:

- The results indicated that faculty employees have an average perception of organizational justice and trust.
- The validity of the standard model, discriminant validity evidence, and structural model were evaluated, and the study's hypotheses were successfully tested.
- The results showed a strong positive relationship between organizational justice and trust.

- The relationship between the various dimensions of justice and organizational trust was analyzed and found to be variable.
- The procedural justice dimension had a strong relationship with organizational trust.
- We did not find a significant relationship between "distributive justice" and "transactional justice" with organizational trust.

5.2. Discussion and Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the field study conducted at the University of Djelfa's colleges, a comprehensive strategy can be proposed to enhance the work environment by promoting fairness and organizational trust among administrative staff. This strategy encompasses a range of initiatives, from strategic aspects aligning with a long-term vision and progressing to daily practical tactics contributing to a positive and sustainable work environment. These suggestions can enhance fairness and organizational trust, positively impacting institutional performance.

A. Strategic Aspects:

- *Promoting Positive Leadership:* Promoting positive leadership requires developing college leaders' skills in effective listening and fair decision-making, which builds trust between management and employees. Furthermore, leadership stability, through maintaining the heads of departments and interests, strengthens organizational relationships and reduces anxiety and tension among employees, leading to a more stable work environment. Leadership stability builds trust and belonging and motivates employees. Leadership change causes anxiety and negatively impacts organizational trust and performance.

- *Improving organizational justice through flexible policies:* Enhancing organizational justice requires reviewing distribution policies to ensure fair incentives based on individual performance. Procedural justice is also enhanced by involving administrative staff in decision-making processes. This approach contributes to creating a work environment that values efforts and enhances employees' sense of belonging and fairness within the organization, which supports organizational loyalty and encourages optimal performance.

- *Enhancing Organizational Trust:* Organizational Trust can be enhanced by improving effective communication between management and employees. Establishing open channels that contribute to increased transparency can achieve this. Furthermore, adopting digital systems is an important step to ensure the timely provision of necessary information, which supports informed decision-making and enhances trust.

- *Enhancing participation and innovation:* To foster creativity and institutional engagement, motivating employees to articulate their ideas and partake in decision-making is imperative, thus augmenting their capacity for innovation. Moreover, implementing procedures like opinion polls and advisory committees fosters communal decision-making and bolsters the administrative staff's sense of accountability and affiliation with the university.

B. Implementation Aspects:

- *Developing a Work Culture:* Developing a work culture requires fostering a vibrant professional conscience by providing ongoing professional training opportunities and linking performance to rewards to motivate employees to improve continuously. Organizing

psychology training courses can also foster sportsmanship among employees by aiming to develop coping skills and transform challenges into opportunities for growth.

- *Improving Internal Relationships*: Building a psychologically safe environment requires empowering employees to express their opinions freely and without fear of repercussions, which fosters innovation and confidence.

- *Supporting Diversity and Inclusion*: Promoting a culture of inclusion in the workplace can be achieved by organizing workshops and training programs that focus on diversity awareness and mutual respect. This approach creates a work environment that values and benefits from individual differences, fostering a sense of belonging and harmony among all employees.

C. Tactical Aspects:

- *Specific techniques for various job categories*: address the requirements of employees in various job categories; advanced training programs can be provided to seasoned employees to refine their abilities and cultivate their professional potential. Young staff members can be incorporated into college activities via orientation programs that elucidate the university's ideals and facilitate their assimilation into the workplace.

- *Organizing seminars and workshops*: Organizing periodic seminars and workshops is an effective way to raise awareness of the importance of organizational trust. It can enhance employees' understanding of its role in improving the work environment and motivating performance, contributing to building a culture based on mutual trust among all parties.

- *Monitoring and evaluating human resources policies*: To ensure the effectiveness of implemented policies, periodic evaluations using performance evaluation questionnaires to measure their impact on employees are essential. Data analytics techniques can also be employed to measure and analyze the impact of promoting fairness and organizational trust and providing opportunities for continuous improvement.

This strategy will create a work environment that promotes fairness and organizational trust at the University of Djelfa's colleges. However, organizational fairness and trust can only be fully achieved through the joint, interactive efforts of management and employees. Therefore, employees must understand the concepts of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice and be familiar with the university's college practices related to these issues. They must also communicate effectively with the management when they observe any unfair practices. They can also build organizational trust by offering ideas, supporting colleagues, participating in volunteer activities, and positively expressing loyalty to them.

5.3. Future research directions:

Based on the field study results, additional research is needed to understand the impact of organizational justice and trust on the performance of institutions and individuals. It is recommended that in-depth studies be conducted on the factors influencing these concepts and how to enhance them in different organizational environments. Future research can also be developed to deepen the understanding of the relationship between these variables and explore the factors influencing them, as indicated in the following points:

- The role of emotional intelligence as a regulating factor in the relationship between organizational justice and organizational trust;

- Organizational Trust, organizational justice, and organizational commitment: Their impact on organizational citizenship behaviors in a digital business environment;
- The impact of organizational justice on organizational trust in light of organizational change: A field study.
- Organizational justice and organizational trust in the aftermath of mergers and acquisitions.
- The impact of socialization on organizational justice and organizational citizenship behaviors: A comparative study between Arab and Japanese cultures.
- The role of servant leadership in enhancing organizational trust through procedural justice as a mediating variable in higher education institutions.

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Genişletilmiş Özet

Örgütsel adalet, yönetim biliminde temel bir kavramdır ve bireyler ile kurumlar üzerinde önemli etkiler yaratır. Dağıtımsal, işlemsel ve etkileşimsel adalet gibi çeşitli boyutlara sahip olan bu kavram, her bir boyut için özgün yaklaşımlar gerektirir. Kuramsal çalışmalar, örgütsel adaletin iş doyumu, motivasyon ve kuruma bağlılık ile pozitif yönde ilişkili olduğunu ortaya koymuştur. Benzer şekilde, örgütsel güven de iş birliği ve performansı artırmada hayati bir rol oynamaktadır. Güven kendiliğinden oluşmaz; şeffaflık, dürüst iletişim ve adil liderlik yoluyla inşa edilir. Bu unsurlar, güçlü bir örgütsel kültürü destekler ve kurumsal hedeflerin başarısı için gerekli olan sağlıklı bireyler arası ilişkileri teşvik eder.

Celfa Üniversitesi'nde gerçekleştirilen saha çalışması, personelin örgütsel adalet ve güveni genel olarak orta düzeyde algıladığını ortaya koymuştur. Araştırmada kullanılan istatistiksel modellerin geçerliliği kanıtlanmış ve örgütsel adalet ile güven arasında pozitif bir ilişki olduğu hipotezi doğrulanmıştır. Özellikle işlemsel adaletin, örgütsel güven üzerinde anlamlı bir etkisi olduğu gözlemlenirken; dağıtımsal ve etkileşimsel adalet ile güven arasında anlamlı bir ilişki tespit edilememiştir. Bu bulgular, çalışan güvenini ve bağlılığını oluşturmada karar alma sürecinin sonuçtan daha önemli olabileceğini göstermektedir.

Bu bulgular doğrultusunda, üniversite ortamında adalet ve güveni artırmaya yönelik kapsamlı bir strateji önerilmiştir. Adil liderlik uygulamalarının geliştirilmesi, performansa dayalı esnek ödül sistemlerinin benimsenmesi ve personelin karar alma süreçlerine aktif katılımının sağlanması, bu stratejinin temel unsurlarındandır. Yüz yüze ve dijital araçlar aracılığıyla etkin iletişim kurulmalı; çalışanların fikir üretmeleri ve kurumsal faaliyetlere katılımları teşvik edilmelidir. Bu tür stratejik adımlar, şeffaf, katılımcı ve motive edici bir iş ortamı oluşturur.

Stratejinin pratik etkisini artırmak amacıyla, mesleki gelişim programları, psikolojik eğitimler ve çeşitliliğe yönelik atölye çalışmaları düzenlenmelidir. Çalışanların kendilerini özgürce ifade edebilecekleri psikolojik olarak güvenli bir ortam yaratmak, yaratıcılığı ve katılımı artıracaktır. Hem deneyimli hem de yeni personel için özelleştirilmiş girişimler, entegrasyon sürecini kolaylaştırır ve performanslarını yükseltir. İnsan kaynakları politikalarının düzenli olarak değerlendirilmesi ise sürekli iyileşmeyi sağlar. Sonuç olarak, adalet ve güvenin inşası, tüm örgüt üyelerinin ortak sorumluluğudur ve sürdürülebilir gelişim ile yüksek kurumsal performansı destekleyen değerlerin pekiştirilmesini gerektirir.

Addition Informations

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